

Continuous-time structural equation model forests

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Abstract

Structural equation model (SEM) trees and forests are valuable tools for exploring predictors of group differences in SEM parameters. In longitudinal studies in particular, they hold significant potential for investigating heterogeneity in change and dynamics. In past research, longitudinal SEM trees and forests have been predominantly estimated with the R package *semtree*, which, until recently, only allowed the estimation of discrete-time (DT) models. The problem of DT models is that they may lead to biased estimates when measurement intervals are unevenly spaced, which is frequent in longitudinal studies. As a solution to this problem, recent updates in the *semtree* package included SEM trees based on continuous-time (CT) models, which do not require constant intervals and can easily adapt to irregular sampling schemes. This implementation, however, yielded biased results and involved a computational burden that was prohibitive for forests. Only very recent work on score-guided algorithms, along with corresponding software implementations, have made continuous-time SEM forests feasible for empirical practice. In this paper, we present a novel implementation of CT-SEM forests that combines the *ctsemOMX* package for CT modeling, the recursive partitioning infrastructure of the *semtree* package, and the score-guided covariate testing procedures of the *strucchange* package. Next, we systematically examine the performance of CT-SEM forests through a Monte Carlo study and illustrate the approach on empirical data from the Survey of Health, Ageing, and Retirement in Europe. Finally, we explore various alternatives for using the information provided by CT-SEM forests, and discuss the benefits and limitations of the approach.

Keywords: continuous time modeling, recursive partitioning, longitudinal data analysis, panel design, structural equation modeling

Translational abstract

Structural equation model (SEM) trees and forests are useful tools for understanding what factors contribute to differences between groups in how they change over time. In past longitudinal research, the estimation of SEM trees and forests has been primarily performed with the R package *semtree*, which, until recently, only allowed the estimation of discrete-time models. The problem of these models is that they lead to biased estimates when measurement intervals are not evenly spaced, which is frequent in longitudinal studies. As a solution to this problem, recent updates to the *semtree* package allowed to build SEM trees using continuous-time (CT) models, which do not require fixed time intervals and can handle irregular sampling schemes more effectively. This implementation, however, yielded biased results and involved a computational burden that was prohibitive for realistic models. Only very recent advances on methods and software have made it feasible to use continuous-time SEM trees and forests in real-world research. In this paper, we present a novel implementation of continuous-time SEM forests that combines the *ctsemOMX* package for CT modeling, the recursive partitioning infrastructure of the *semtree* package, and the score-guided covariate testing procedures of the *strucchange* package. Next, we examine the performance of our approach using simulated data and illustrate it on empirical data from the Survey of Health, Ageing, and Retirement in Europe. Finally, we explore different ways of using the information provided by continuous-time SEM forests, and discuss the benefits and limitations of the approach.

Continuous-time structural equation model forests

Over the past decades, longitudinal studies have gained traction in psychology, with panel studies being among the most popular designs in the field. Recent technological advances have facilitated the collection of data, and developments in statistical models and software implementations have allowed access to a wide variety of analytic tools. In this context, dynamic models have emerged as a valuable approach to the study of psychological processes due to their flexibility in characterizing change, stability, and lead-lag relations over time. Two often encountered problems in the analysis of panel data, particularly with dynamic models, are: 1) heterogeneity in the spacing between measurements, and 2) parameter heterogeneity across individuals or groups.

Unequally spaced measurements are very common in longitudinal studies: individuals are rarely measured at the same points in time, and the gap between measurements is unlikely to be constant across all occasions. However, researchers often disregard this heterogeneity by artificially creating evenly spaced intervals through binning procedures. Dynamic models implemented under the assumption of equally spaced intervals are called discrete-time (DT) dynamic models. While a DT approach simplifies the structure of the data, it is likely to produce biased estimates when the assumption of equally spaced time intervals is not met (Estrada & Ferrer, 2019; McArdle & Hamagami, 2004; Miller & Ferrer, 2017; Voelkle & Oud, 2015). Moreover, DT models suffer from a problem known as *time-interval dependency* (Gollob & Reichardt, 1987; Ryan & Hamaker, 2022), meaning that the parameters representing the process dynamics are conditional on the particular time interval used, and thus inferences based on these parameters are not valid for other time intervals.

A natural solution to the problem of unequally spaced measurements is to use continuous-time (CT) dynamic models (Oud & Jansen, 2000; van Montfort et al., 2018; Voelkle et al., 2012). In CT models, the time-specific observations are considered discrete realizations of an underlying process that unfolds continuously over time. That is, although the process of interest is measured at specific occasions, it does not stop existing between observations, nor does it change in discrete steps. From a theoretical standpoint, the assumptions of CT models align more closely with current theories of change, in which many psychological processes are assumed to evolve continuously. Moreover, CT models yield estimates that are independent of the time lag, which provides at least two practical advantages: 1) they can account for time intervals of any length, be they equal or unequal across occasions or individuals, and 2) the CT estimates can be transformed into DT estimates for any arbitrary time lag, thus allowing inferences across different time intervals (see Voelkle et al., 2012).

Parameter heterogeneity, on the other hand, refers to differences between groups of individuals in the parameters of the model, which reflect differences in the observed data patterns. For example, in a longitudinal study of emotion regulation, parameter heterogeneity might reflect group differences in the rate at which their negative emotion changes (e.g., some individuals might experience rapid fluctuations, while others might exhibit more stable patterns). Detecting and understanding the sources of parameter heterogeneity is an important challenge for methodological and empirical researchers, and multiple methods have been proposed to address this issue. One of the most popular approaches are models with random effects. These models allow including between-individual variances in specific components of the model, such as intercepts or slopes. Notably, recent extensions of these models, such as hierarchical Bayesian models (see Driver & Voelkle, 2018) or dynamic structural equation models (see Asparouhov et al.,

2018; McNeish & Hamaker, 2020), allow capturing individual variation in all parameters of the model, including regression effects. In all these models, covariates can be incorporated to explain between-individual differences in variables or parameters. In empirical studies, however, the number of potential explanatory covariates is often too large to be tested manually. Moreover, individual differences in dynamics may be explained not only by the main effects of these covariates, but also by intricate non-linear interactions between them, making the search for relevant effects infeasible with large datasets.

Originally introduced in the field of machine learning, model-based recursive partitioning provides a formal avenue to the problem of parameter heterogeneity in large panel datasets (for an overview see Strobl et al., 2008; Zeileis et al., 2008). Model-based recursive partitioning is a general paradigm that combines decision tree algorithms with parametric models. These algorithms, also called model-based trees, split the sample into homogeneous groups of individuals that differ with respect to the parameters of a pre-specified model, while identifying the most relevant predictors of group differences in the process. Applied to dynamic models, model-based trees allow for: a) identifying and characterizing groups of individuals with different dynamics, and b) describing how a set of predictors and their interactions are related to linear or non-linear differences in such dynamics. One of the strengths of model-based trees is their interpretability, as they can be represented as a tree-like hierarchical structure that effectively illustrates the split decisions made by the algorithm. Unfortunately, they are also very sensitive to random sampling fluctuations, meaning that fitting a tree to different samples of the same population may lead to completely different tree structures (for a demonstration, see Strobl et al., 2009). Consequently, the results of a model-based tree may not be reliable. This problem can be solved by building an ensemble of model-based trees, also

known as a model-based forest. Although forests lack the interpretability of single trees, they provide measures of *variable importance*, which are robust and reliable estimates of the average impact of each covariate on the prediction of parameter heterogeneity.

In behavioral sciences, large panel data sets are often analyzed within the framework of structural equation models (SEM). Although these models have been typically estimated in discrete time, recent software developments, such as the *ctsemOMX* and *ctsem* packages (Driver et al., 2017; Driver & Voelkle, 2018) for the statistical software language R (R Core Team, 2022), have made continuous-time modeling more accessible for researchers. The recursive partitioning of SEMs, which is referred to as SEM trees, and the ensembles of SEM trees, which are referred to as SEM forests, are almost exclusively performed with the *semtree* package (Brandmaier et al., 2013, 2016). The first application of SEM trees to CT models came from Brandmaier et al. (2018) and was implemented by pairing the *ctsemOMX* and *semtree* packages. Unfortunately, this approach was limited in practical terms due to excessive runtime and suboptimal covariate testing strategies (see Arnold et al., 2021). As a consequence, the combination of SEM forests with CT models has not yet been possible due to the lack of appropriate software.

In this manuscript, we introduce an approach to recursively partition continuous-time SEMs, and present the first software implementation, systematic evaluation, and empirical application of CT-SEM forests. To this end, we combined the R package *ctsemOMX*, for the specification and estimation of continuous-time models, with the recursive partitioning infrastructure of the *semtree* package. Importantly, our implementation uses a covariate selection procedure based on structural change tests, also called score-based tests (Merkle et al., 2014; Merkle & Zeileis, 2013), which is included in the *semtree* package (see Arnold et al., 2021). This strategy significantly

improves upon the original CT-SEM trees in terms of computational runtime and covariate selection, making CT-SEM trees, and particularly CT-SEM forests, more practical for applied research.

The remainder of the article is organized as follows. First, we introduce continuous-time models, CT-SEM trees guided by score-based tests, and CT-SEM forests. Second, we conduct a Monte Carlo study to systematically examine the performance of CT-SEM forests. Third, we use an empirical example to illustrate the specification, estimation, and interpretation of a CT-SEM forest. Finally, we make recommendations on how to use the information provided by CT-SEM forests and discuss the advantages and limitations of the approach. Annotated code for replicating the empirical example, as well as some of the figures and algorithms presented in this manuscript are provided in the supplementary materials at:

https://osf.io/xqgbs/?view_only=7fdca12b9dd14a499aae5caeab72484c.

Dynamic models: From discrete to continuous time

Dynamic models are based on the idea that the state of a system at any given time is determined by its own history and initial conditions, as well as any external forces or “shocks” that may affect it as it unfolds over time. There are different ways of formalizing these ideas into equations, depending on the statistical framework and the type of data being analyzed (see Oud & Singer, 2008). In the context of discrete-time SEM, the evolution of a dynamic system over time can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{x}_{i,t} = \mathbf{A}_{\Delta t} \mathbf{x}_{i,t-1} + \boldsymbol{\xi}_{\Delta t,i} + \mathbf{b}_{\Delta t} + \mathbf{w}_{\Delta t,i} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_{i,t}$ is a vector of l variables representing the level of each individual i at time t .

The $l \times l$ matrix $\mathbf{A}_{\Delta t}$ contains the relations between variables over time (with autoregressive effects in the main diagonal and cross-lagged effects in the off-

diagonals). The l -variate vector $\xi_{\Delta t, i}$ captures stable between-individual differences, and its elements are often referred to as trait variables or random intercepts. The l -variate vector $\mathbf{b}_{\Delta t}$ contains DT intercepts that capture non-zero trajectories or equilibrium points (i.e., the long-term level at which the process fluctuates around). Finally, $\mathbf{w}_{\Delta t}$ is a dynamic error term that captures the impact of random shocks on the system over time. These dynamic errors are normally distributed with a covariance matrix $\mathbf{Q}_{\Delta t}$ of dimensions $l \times l$.

Importantly, Equation 1 describes the changes in $\mathbf{x}_{i, t}$ over a specific time interval Δt , which is assumed to be constant across all measurements and individuals. As sketched above, this time-interval dependency severely limits the utility of DT models, for example, because different researchers studying the same process in different time intervals would not be able to compare the strength of the effects found. To overcome this limitation, we need to estimate parameters that are independent of the time lag, which requires adopting a CT approach.

Continuous-time models use differential equations to describe change in the process of interest, which is assumed to unfold in continuous time. The formulation of a CT model can be summarized in three steps:

- 1) Compute the derivative of $\mathbf{x}(t)$ with respect to time.
- 2) Solve the differential equation for t_0 and any arbitrary time interval ($\Delta t = t - t_0$).
- 3) Constrain the DT parameters in Equation 1 to the solution of step 2.

Step 1. Taking the derivative of $\mathbf{x}(t)$ with respect to time leads to a stochastic differential equation that describes the change in \mathbf{x} (i.e., $d\mathbf{x}(t)$) as a function of its current level $\mathbf{x}(t)$:

$$d\mathbf{x}_i(t) = (\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_i(t) + \boldsymbol{\xi}_i + \mathbf{b})dt + \mathbf{G}d\mathbf{W}_i(t) \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{A} is a $l \times l$ drift matrix including auto-and cross-effects (i.e., the CT equivalent to autoregressive and cross-lagged effects), $\boldsymbol{\xi}_i$ is a trait variable (or random intercept), \mathbf{b} is a $l \times 1$ vector of CT intercepts, and the stochastic term $\mathbf{G}d\mathbf{W}(t)$ is a continuous-time dynamic error process, with a $l \times l$ covariance matrix $\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{G}\mathbf{G}'$ (also called diffusion matrix). $\mathbf{W}(t)$ represents a Wiener process, which is the continuous-time form of a random walk, and \mathbf{G} is a Cholesky triangle that quantifies the effect of \mathbf{W} on the change in $\mathbf{x}(t)$. Note that the key difference between Equations 1 and 2 lies in the treatment of time. In the DT equation (Eq. 1), the change in \mathbf{x} occurs over a time interval of $\Delta t = 1$, whereas in the CT equation (Eq. 2), the change in \mathbf{x} occurs over an infinitesimally small time interval dt .

Step 2. Once the derivative of the dynamic equation is formulated, it has to be solved for the starting point $\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{x}(t_0)$ and a time interval ($\Delta t = t - t_0$), which leads to the following equation:

$$\mathbf{x}_i(t) = \mathbf{e}^{\mathbf{A}\cdot\Delta t}\mathbf{x}_i(t_0) + (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{e}^{\mathbf{A}\cdot\Delta t})\boldsymbol{\xi}_i + \mathbf{A}^{-1}[\mathbf{e}^{\mathbf{A}\cdot\Delta t} - \mathbf{I}]\mathbf{b} + \mathbf{w}_i(\Delta t) \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{w}(\Delta t)$ is the integral function of a Wiener process. For a detailed description of this function, and for the relationship between DT and CT parameters, we refer the readers to Voelkle et al. (2012).

Step 3. Once the derivative is solved, parameters in Equation 1 can be constrained according to Equation 3, which yields the relationship between DT and CT. To illustrate this relationship, let us suppose that we use Equation 3 to represent the dynamics of two processes (e.g., positive and negative affect) measured at constant intervals of one day ($\Delta t = 1$) across all measurements and individuals. Figure 1 shows the path diagram of this bivariate model, which is a continuous-time version the popular random intercept

cross-lagged panel model (RI-CLPM; Hamaker et al., 2015; Kenny & Zautra, 2001).

Presume we obtain a drift matrix as follows after fitting the model to the data:

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.5 & 0.17 \\ 0.17 & -0.5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

If we plug these estimates into Equation 3, we obtain the following results (note that we applied some rounding):

$$\mathbf{x}_i(t) = \begin{bmatrix} 0.6 & 0.1 \\ 0.1 & 0.6 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_i(t_0) + \begin{bmatrix} 0.4 & 0.9 \\ 0.9 & 0.4 \end{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\xi}_i + \begin{bmatrix} 0.8 & 0 \\ 0.06 & 0.8 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{b} + \mathbf{W}(1) \quad (5)$$

Equation 5 indicates that, for time intervals of one day, the levels of positive and negative affect (\mathbf{x}) at any point in time depend on the levels of positive and negative affect on the day before (denoted by autoregressive coefficients of 0.6 and cross-lagged coefficients of 0.1). Of course, if the distance between measurements is always $\Delta t = 1$, fitting a DT model would lead to the exact same parameters in Equation 5. However, the advantage of CT models is that it is possible to study the parameters of a process at time intervals different to the ones used for collecting the data. For example, solving Equation 3 for a time interval of five days yields the following parameter estimates:

$$\mathbf{x}_i(t) = \begin{bmatrix} 0.03 & 0.04 \\ 0.04 & 0.03 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_i(t_0) + \begin{bmatrix} 0.97 & 0.96 \\ 0.96 & 0.97 \end{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\xi}_i + \begin{bmatrix} 1.94 & 0.59 \\ 0.59 & 1.94 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{b} + \mathbf{W}(5) \quad (6)$$

A comparison between Equations 4 and 5 reveals that autoregressive and cross-lagged parameters are smaller when measurements are farther from each other, meaning that the strength of the discrete time relationships shrinks as more time passes—that is, our affect yesterday is more predictive of our affect today than our affect in five days.

[Insert Figure 1 here]

In summary, the parameters provided by CT models can be transformed into DT parameters for any given time interval. This relationship makes CT parameters more interpretable and has at least three practical advantages: 1) it allows capturing dynamics

for different time scales (e.g., the strength of a cross-effect for time lags of one day, one week, etc.), 2) it allows comparing parameters that were estimated using different time intervals, facilitating cross-study comparisons and meta-analyses (Dormann et al., 2020; Guthier et al., 2020; Kuiper & Ryan, 2020), and 3) it allows accounting for time intervals of varying length, both across measurements and individuals. Furthermore, the ability of CT models to capture the underlying behavior of a process across different time intervals has substantial implications for parameter interpretation and hypothesis testing. For example, DT parameters may lead to wrong conclusions regarding the size, direction, and presence or absence of an effect, as this effect may be zero for some time intervals but positive or negative for others (see Driver, 2024). Parameterizing the model as a system of differential equations offers a solution to this problem.

Structural equation model trees

SEM trees, as introduced by Brandmaier et al. (2013), are an instance of model-based recursive partitioning designed for exploring heterogeneity in the parameters of a structural equation model. The rationale of SEM trees in longitudinal data analysis is as follows: given a collection of repeated measures, a set of observed covariates, and a pre-specified template SEM, an algorithm recursively searches across all covariates and their possible partitions to identify subgroups of individuals who differ with respect to a set of SEM parameters. Thus, SEM trees are capable of detecting heterogeneity in dynamics as long as the parameter differences can be predicted by the covariates at hand.

Figure 2 exemplifies a SEM tree applied to artificial data. Following our previous example, let us suppose that the data contains repeated measures of positive and negative affect over time, a template model as shown in Figure 1, and three covariates: sex (male or female), handedness (right or left), and age at the first

measurement occasion. For simplicity, we will focus only on group differences with respect to auto-and cross-effects. As illustrated in Figure 2, SEM trees form a hierarchical structure of binary splits represented by nodes, each containing a SEM fitted to a distinct subsample. A node can either have two successors (daughter nodes) and is called an *inner node* (e.g., node 2 in Figure 2) or no successors and is called a *leaf* or *terminal node* (e.g., nodes 3, 4, and 5 in Figure 2). The node at the top of the tree has no parent nodes and is called the *root node* (e.g., node 1 in Figure 2). Inner nodes contain split decisions with respect to a specific predictor (e.g., sex or age), and a cut point in the predictor (e.g., individuals younger and older than 60 years). Finally, each leaf node contains a subgroup of individuals described by a set of SEM parameter estimates. Note that handedness is not included in Figure 1, meaning that the algorithm did not detect any parameter heterogeneity associated with this covariate.

[Insert Figure 2 here]

An important aspect of recursive partitioning algorithms is the decision rule, which guides the process of covariate and split selection. Model-based trees generally use decision rules based on goodness-of-fit criteria, meaning that, in each node of the tree, the algorithm searches for the predictor-guided split that minimizes the misfit between models and individuals. These rules can be implemented in different ways, depending on the statistical framework and estimation method used. Originally, the SEM trees implemented in the *semtree* package used a covariate testing procedure based on likelihood ratios (Brandmaier et al. 2013). This required the estimation of a multi-group SEM for each potential split in each covariate, which was repeatedly compared with the template SEM through a series of likelihood ratio tests. This approach was computationally burdensome and became very slow in datasets with many covariates, especially when the covariates had many unique values (see Arnold et al., 2021).

Furthermore, a problem of likelihood-ratio-based selection procedures is that the resulting trees are unstable when the subsamples in the nodes become small.

A computationally faster and more stable alternative to likelihood-ratio tests are score-based tests (Zeileis, 2005; Zeileis & Hornik, 2007), which monitor fluctuations in the individual contributions to the fitting function (also known as scores) to test potential predictors of heterogeneity. In the R environment, the package *strucchange* (Zeileis et al., 2002) offers a unified framework for implementing score-based tests with a wide range of model classes. This framework is employed by other packages for model-based recursive partitioning, such as *party* (Zeileis et al., 2008) and *partykit* (Hothorn & Zeileis, 2015), and was recently implemented in the *semtree* package by Arnold et al. (2021). The resulting score-guided SEM trees provide unbiased covariate selection, high statistical power, and compute much faster than the original SEM trees. For these reasons, the CT-SEM trees and forests presented in this manuscript use predictor and split selection procedures guided by score-based tests.

The first requirement for growing a SEM tree is the specification of a template SEM. This model reflects hypotheses about the mechanisms of change governing the data, the associations between latent constructs, and their relations with the observed variables. Once the template model is specified, the algorithm for score-guided SEM trees can be summarized in three steps (see Arnold et al., 2021):

1. Fit the template SEM to all individuals in the current node.
2. Assess whether the SEM parameter estimates are constant or vary with respect to a covariate.
3. Select the covariate, and the split point in said covariate, associated with the largest group differences. If the difference exceeds a threshold, split the sample

associated with the current node into two subsamples, and repeat the procedure in both child nodes. Otherwise terminate.

Step 1. Model estimation

In structural equation models, the observed structure of the data is generally expressed as an observed vector of means $\bar{\mathbf{y}}$ and covariance matrix \mathbf{S} . Our implementation of CT-SEM trees uses the *ctsemOMX* package for model estimation. Internally, this package constraints the DT parameters to the underlying CT parameters for every unique interval according to Equation 3. Next, based on the model equations, it computes a model-implied vector of means $\boldsymbol{\mu}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ and covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$, which are expressed as a function of a vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ of CT model parameters. The CT parameters in $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ are then estimated by minimizing a fitting function that quantifies the discrepancy between $\bar{\mathbf{y}}$ and $\boldsymbol{\mu}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$, as well as the discrepancy between \mathbf{S} and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$. For multivariate normal data, the following row-wise maximum log-likelihood function is used for each individual:

$$\ln L(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \mathbf{y}_i) = \frac{1}{2} \{ [\mathbf{y}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}(\boldsymbol{\theta})]^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}(\boldsymbol{\theta})^{-1} [\mathbf{y}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}(\boldsymbol{\theta})] + \ln[\det(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}(\boldsymbol{\theta}))] + p \ln(2\pi) \} \quad (7)$$

where i indicates individuals and p is the number of observed variables. Note that in CT models the model-implied vector of means and covariance matrix are a function of the time interval. Thus, in situations where the time intervals vary across individuals, some of the computations necessary to minimize Equation 7 have to be performed separately for each set of unique time intervals, which may lead to high computational runtimes.

Step 2. Evaluation of predictors

The second step involves searching among all covariates to find the most relevant predictor in the current node—that is, the predictor that explains most of the parameter heterogeneity. For this, the score-based algorithm first computes the case-

wise partial derivatives of the log-likelihood function (Equation 7) with respect to each of the model parameters and evaluates the expression at the estimates:

$$\mathbf{s}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}; \mathbf{y}_i) = \left[\frac{\partial \ln L(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}; \mathbf{y}_i)}{\partial \hat{\theta}_1}, \dots, \frac{\partial \ln L(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}; \mathbf{y}_i)}{\partial \hat{\theta}_q} \right]^T \quad (8)$$

The results are stored in a $N \times q$ matrix, where N is the number of individuals in the current node and q is the number of parameters. These case-wise derivatives, also called scores, indicate the extent to which an individual's log-likelihood is maximized by the model parameters (i.e., how well an individual is represented by the model parameters). Thus, scores close to zero indicate a good fit between model and individual, whereas scores further away from zero point to a stronger misfit.

The derivatives of the log-likelihood function can be computed either analytically or numerically. In *semtree*, scores are computed analytically following the *sparse derivative algorithm* proposed by von Oertzen & Brick (2014). However, this analytic solution is restricted to linear SEMs. As demonstrated in Equation 3, some parameters of the CT models are arguments of non-linear functions such as the exponential matrix, and thus the analytic solution is not applicable. Alternatively, the numerical solution requires to repeatedly compute the scores for each unique set of time intervals, which may lead to increased computational costs in databases with individual differences in the time intervals. To solve this problem, we implemented an algorithm that numerically approximates the derivatives of the matrix exponential function and derives the other parts analytically. This approach approximates the derivative of the matrix exponential function very closely, allows the computation of continuous-time scores, and is computationally more efficient than a fully numerical approach. The complete algorithm can be found in the *ctsemScores.R* file at https://osf.io/xqgbs/?view_only=7fdca12b9dd14a499aae5caeab72484c.

Next, the score matrix is accumulated according to the order induced by the covariate under evaluation. For example, for the covariate *age*, the first row of the matrix will correspond to the youngest individual. In the second row, the scores of the youngest and second youngest individuals are summed up, and so on. This process leads to a $N \times q$ matrix of *cumulative* scores and can be formalized as:

$$CSP(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}; s) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} I(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}})^{-1/2} \sum_{h=1}^s S(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}; \mathbf{y}_h) \quad (9)$$

where the index s denotes the number of sorted individuals entering the equation, and h indicates the sorted individuals until $h = s$. The $q \times q$ matrix $I(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}})^{-1/2}$ is the half-squared inverse of the Fisher information matrix, and its purpose is to decorrelate the scores of the q parameter estimates so that they are independent from each other.

In order to test the null hypothesis of parameter homogeneity, the CSP matrix is aggregated into a single scalar, which serves as a test statistic. This statistic quantifies the degree of parameter heterogeneity associated with a given covariate. Different ways of aggregating the CSP matrix will lead to test statistics with different properties. In our implementation of SEM trees, we use different score-based test statistics depending on the nature of the covariates (Hjort & Koning, 2002; Merkle et al., 2014; Merkle & Zeileis, 2013). A detailed description of these statistics is provided in Appendix A (see also Arnold et al. 2021). The complete algorithms for computing the derivatives of the log-likelihood function and aggregating the CSP matrix are accessible in the supplementary materials.

Step 3. Predictor and split selection

The selection of a predictor involves computing the previous test statistic for every covariate given to the SEM tree. If the null hypothesis of parameter homogeneity

is rejected for two or more covariates, the p -values of their test statistics are compared, and the covariate associated with the smallest p -value is selected for splitting. Once the predictor is selected, a single cut point must be located. For this, the CSP matrix is summed row-wise into a vector in such a way that each unique value of the sorted predictor is paired with a specific value of this vector. The optimal cut point is found by splitting the sample after the observation associated with the maximum of this vector. After the split, Steps 1-3 are repeated recursively for each subsequent node until there are no more available covariates or some pre-specified stopping criterion is reached (e.g., a minimum sample size or a maximum number of partitions).

Structural equation model forests

A problem of the decision tree algorithms used for growing SEM trees is that they are greedy algorithms: they seek the optimal split at each level without considering how that decision will affect the overall fit several levels down. Although this typically leads to a reasonably good solution, it is not guaranteed to be the optimal solution. On top of this, split decisions are extremely sensitive to sampling fluctuations. That is, the predictors selected, as well as their cut points and resulting partitions, strongly depend on the specific distribution of the observed data, meaning that just a predictor or a cut point selected differently can potentially alter the entire structure of the tree (for an empirical illustration of this problem, see Strobl et al., 2009). One consequence of this is that the relative position of the predictors in a SEM tree may not be a reliable indicator of their importance. SEM forests provide a formal avenue to these problems.

SEM forests, as first presented by Brandmaier et al. (2016), are ensembles of SEM trees in which individuals and predictors are randomly sampled from the original dataset. As demonstrated elsewhere (Breiman, 2001; Bühlmann & Yu, 2002), the predictive performance of a random forest is maximized when its constituent trees are

as diverse or independent from one another as possible. Thus, the instability of trees is used here as an advantage, as growing each tree on a random subsample is likely to result in a diverse set of tree structures, while maintaining the same data generation process. The process of randomly sampling individuals is called *bootstrap aggregating* (bagging) when it is done with replacement (Breiman, 1996) and *pasting* or *subsampling* when it is done without replacement (Breiman, 1999). In general, subsampling may be preferable, as it is less prone to selection bias than bagging (Strobl et al., 2007). To further increase the diversity of the tree structures, the covariates entering each tree are only a random subset of the total list of covariates. Note that growing SEM trees on the same covariates would cause stronger predictors to always prevail over weaker predictors, preventing them from entering the forest. In contrast, randomizing the covariates gives weaker predictors a chance to be included in a tree, which may reveal interaction effects that would be missed otherwise.

The algorithm for growing a SEM forest can be summarized as follows. Let K be the total number of trees in the forest. For each tree $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$:

1. Select a random subset of individuals D_k^{train} (using either bagging or pasting) and store the undrawn individuals in an *out-of-bag sample* D_k^{OOB} .
2. Select a random subset of candidate predictors (i.e., covariates) to search for partitions. The number of candidate predictors that enter each tree (c) is heuristically determined here as $c = \log_2(m)$, where m is the total number of covariates in the original dataset¹.
3. Grow a SEM tree on the dataset D_k^{train} . Repeat steps 1-3 until $k = K$.

¹ The number of candidate predictors is typically heuristically chosen as either \sqrt{c} , $c/3$, or $c = \log_2(c)$, among others (see Breiman, 2001). Modifying this value is possible in *semtree*. For a review of the relative advantages of increasing or reducing the number of candidate predictors, see Probst et al., (2019).

The SEM trees that constitute a SEM forest can be aggregated to compute *variable importance* measures. These are indicators of how much each covariate contributes to the prediction of a response, which in SEM forests takes the form of an observed vector of means and covariance matrix. In the following, we briefly describe how to compute and interpret this measure.

Variable importance

In SEM forests, variable importance is computed through a procedure called *permutation accuracy importance*. This algorithm randomly permutes the covariates in each SEM tree to break their association with the model-predicted distribution. Note that, when a covariate is selected as a relevant predictor of heterogeneity, the resulting partition should lead to a better fit between models and individuals. Permuting the predictor changes the group membership of some individuals, which is equivalent to randomly distributing them across the leaf nodes of the tree. As a result, individuals who are randomly assigned to a different leaf are expected to fit the new set of SEM parameters more poorly, leading to an overall increase in model misfit. By averaging the increase in misfit across all trees in the forest on the out-of-bag samples (D_k^{OOB}), an estimate of variable importance is obtained for each predictor. SEM forests, as implemented in the *semtree* package, rely on maximum likelihood estimation, and thus use the log-likelihood (see Equation 7) as an indicator of model misfit. Evaluated at the parameter estimates ($\hat{\theta}$) and summed over all individuals, Equation 7 yields a scalar that quantifies the fit between the model and the data, with higher absolute values pointing to a stronger misfit. The total misfit of a SEM tree is calculated by summing the log-likelihoods of the models across all leaf nodes.

Figure 3 illustrates the variable importance measures of a hypothetical SEM forest following the example of Figure 2. The covariate *Sex* was selected as the most important predictor, with a variable importance estimate of 230. This means that randomly permuting this predictor (and thus removing its effect) led to an average increase of 230 in log-likelihood across all trees. A similar interpretation can be made for *age*, which obtained a variable importance estimate of 45. Finally, the importance of *handedness* was estimated as zero. This may occur either because *handedness* was not selected in any of the trees, or because permuting *handedness* resulted in equal increases and decreases of log-likelihood across trees (e.g., +10 in one tree and -10 in another tree). Negative values of variable importance are possible when an irrelevant covariate is selected in one or more trees, and the subsequent permutation results in an improvement of the log-likelihood—that is, in a better fit between model and individuals. Although the SEM tree algorithm should not perform partitions based on irrelevant covariates, there is always a probability of a type I error.

[Insert Figure 3 here]

In the context of SEM forests, variable importance has at least two important benefits (Brandmaier et al., 2016): 1) it summarizes the predictive performance of each covariate into a single value, and it does so by considering their interactions with other covariates across all trees, and 2) it can take into account all the parameters in the model, instead of being restricted to a specific variable or relation in that model. Thus, variable importance provides robust summary information about how a set of predictor variables relates to an outcome model. Given a particular theory, the information provided by variable importance measures may reveal important covariate effects that had not been considered before. This information, in turn, can be used to modify the original parametric model (e.g., including some of the most relevant covariates as

predictors of parameter heterogeneity), thus improving its explanatory value. Nevertheless, it is important to note that the information provided by variable importance estimates is highly aggregated. Thus, it may not always be clear how a certain predictor affects the model or how to incorporate such predictor in the model, particularly in models with many parameters. In the Discussion section, below, we explore different uses and applications of variable importance.

Continuous-time SEM forests

The combination of CT models with SEM forests is a promising framework that can advance our understanding of between-individual differences in psychological processes. However, the implementation of CT-SEM forests poses some challenges in terms of stability and computational efficiency. Due to the integrations required, CT models are more complex compared to traditional structural equation models, and certain estimation problems, such as local solutions, are more frequent. Also, CT models are more computationally demanding than DT models because the parameter constraints are a function of the time intervals. Thus, the number of computations increases with the number of unique time intervals in the dataset, which may lead to excessive runtimes. These problems are aggravated in CT-SEM forests, as the template SEM needs to be estimated once in each node of each tree.

Simulation study

Data generation

To evaluate the performance of CT-SEM forests, we generated waves of data representing two observed processes x_1 and x_2 with unevenly spaced measurements that varied across both measurement occasions and individuals. These intervals were generated from a uniform distribution bounded by 0.6 and 1.4. The longitudinal

processes were generated according to the model presented in Figure 1, which can be expressed as:

$$d \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_{1[i]} \\ \mathbf{x}_{2[i]} \end{bmatrix} (t) = \left(\begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_{1[i]} \\ \mathbf{x}_{2[i]} \end{bmatrix} (t) + \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\xi}_{x1[i]} \\ \boldsymbol{\xi}_{x2[i]} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{b}_{x1} \\ \mathbf{b}_{x2} \end{bmatrix} \right) dt + \mathbf{G} d \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{w}_{x1[i]} \\ \mathbf{w}_{x2[i]} \end{bmatrix} (t) \quad [10]$$

The details of each simulation condition in terms of, parameter heterogeneity (homogeneous vs. heterogeneous data), type of covariates (i.e., informative vs. noise) sample size (N) and number of repeated measures (T) are described below:

- 1) Study 1. Homogeneous data and 15 noise covariates, with $N = 1000$ and $T = 4$.
- 2) Study 2. Heterogeneous data and 15 noise covariates, with $N = 1000$ and $T = 4$.
- 3) Study 3. Heterogeneous data, 4 informative covariates, and 11 noise covariates, with the following combinations of N and T :
 - a. Condition 1: $T = 4$ and $N = 400$.
 - b. Condition 2: $T = 4$ and $N = 1000$.
 - c. Condition 3: $T = 10$ and $N = 400$.
 - d. Condition 4: $T = 10$ and $N = 1000$.

The number of replications used (i.e., the number of CT-SEM forests estimated) was 200 for Study 1 and Study 2, and 200 for each condition in Study 3. Across all studies and conditions, we used 1000 trees in each forest.

Study 1. Homogeneous data and noise covariates

In this study we evaluated the performance of CT-SEM forests and trees in scenarios where all individuals were characterized by a single set of parameters and none of the covariates was a relevant predictor of parameter heterogeneity. This

evaluation was based on two metrics: type I error rates (i.e., proportion of false-positive splits across trees) and variable importance estimates. To ensure optimal type I error rates, we implemented a Bonferroni procedure to adjust the p -values of score-based tests, limiting the proportion of false-positive splits in a tree to 5%. Consequently, a CT-SEM forest that works correctly should present around 5% of split trees and near-zero variable importance estimates for all covariates.

Study 2. Heterogeneous data and noise covariates

The goal of this study was to evaluate the performance of CT-SEM forests and their constituent trees in scenarios where there was parameter heterogeneity, but none of the covariates was a relevant predictor of heterogeneity. We generated samples consisting of five groups (G1 to G5), each one characterized by a unique set of parameter values, which are presented in Table 1 in discrete-time form for a time interval of $\Delta t = 1$. For simplicity, only the parameters of the drift matrix (\mathbf{A}) and the random intercepts' covariance matrix ($\mathbf{\Psi}$) were varied across groups, while keeping the remaining parameters constant. We opted for parameter values of 0 and 1 for the means and standard deviations of the initial states, respectively, to simulate data that is centered and standardized with respect to the initial measurement occasion (both common practices in longitudinal analyses). In each sample, we generated 15 random covariates that were unrelated to the parameters characterizing the longitudinal processes. To make the simulation more representative of real-world scenarios, these covariates were created using different scales of measurement (i.e., continuous, ordinal, multinomial, or dichotomous), although these variations were not expected to affect the performance of CT-SEM trees and forests (for a detailed description of the covariates, see Appendix B).

Table 1.

Generating parameters for the simulation Study 2. The parameters are shown in discrete-time for a time interval of $\Delta t = 1$.

Parameter	Study 1	Studies 2 and 3				
		G1	G2	G3	G4	G5
Autoregressive effect on x_1 (a_{11})	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.6	0.4
Cross-lagged effects of x_2 on x_1 (a_{12})	0.2	0	-0.2	0.2	-0.2	-0.1
Cross-lagged effects of x_1 on x_2 (a_{21})	-0.1	0	0.2	0.3	-0.1	-0.2
Autoregressive effect on x_2 (a_{22})	0.4	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.4	0.6
Random intercept variance of x_1 ($\sigma_{\xi 11}^2$)	1	4	1	3	1	4
Random intercept variance of x_2 ($\sigma_{\xi 22}^2$)	1	4	1	3	1	4
Random intercept covariance ($\sigma_{\xi 12}$)	0.4	1.6	-0.4	1.8	-0.6	0
Diffusion variance of x_1 ($\sigma_{q 11}^2$)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Diffusion variance of x_2 ($\sigma_{q 22}^2$)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Diffusion covariance ($\sigma_{q 12}$)	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Continuous-time intercept of x_1 (b_{x1})	0	0	0	0	0	0
Continuous-time intercept of x_2 (b_{x2})	0	0	0	0	0	0

In this study, we assessed the performance of CT-SEM forests based on two metrics: proportion of forests with at least one tree split and variable importance estimates. The same Bonferroni procedure used in Study 1 was implemented to adjust the p -values of score-based tests, limiting the proportion of false-positive splits within a tree to 5%. Consequently, a CT-SEM forest that works correctly should present around 5% of split trees and near-zero variable importance estimates for all covariates.

Study 3. Heterogeneous data and informative covariates

In this [study](#) we investigated the ability of CT-SEM forests to capture the true order of importance of a set of informative covariates. For this, we generated four relevant predictors of parameter heterogeneity ($P1$, $P2$, $P3$, and $P4$) based on the splits presented in Figure 4 and eleven non-informative (i.e., noise) covariates. Both informative and non-informative covariates were generated with different scales of measurement, as described before (see Appendix B). A correct variable importance analysis is expected to identify $P1$ as the most important predictor, followed by $P2$ and $P3$, in that order. The predictor with the lowest importance should be $P4$, although it should still be more relevant than the 11 non-informative covariates, which are expected to have near-zero estimates.

[Insert Figure 4 here]

We evaluated this under four combinations of number of repeated measures (T) and sample size (N): C1) $T = 4$, $N = 400$; C2) $T = 4$, $N = 1000$, C3) $T = 10$, $N = 400$, and C4) $T = 10$, $N = 1000$. In all conditions, a CT-SEM forest was fitted to each replication using the CT model described in Figure 1 and Equation 10 as the template model. For simplicity, we used a constraint that computes the means and (co)variances of the first occasion as functions of the other parameters. Consequently, only the 12 parameters in Table 1 were freely estimated. The CT model was specified and estimated with the *ctsemOMX* package (Driver et al., 2017), and then passed to the *semtree* package (Brandmaier et al., 2013, 2016) for growing the forest and computing variable importance estimates. The scores were calculated as described in the section *structural equation model trees*, whereas the score-guided test statistics for covariate testing and split selection were computed using functions of the *strucchange* package (Zeileis et al., 2002).

Results

Proportion of Type I Errors

In Study 1 and Study 2, every tree in a forest with more than one node was considered a type I error. Ideally, the percentage of type I errors (i.e., the percentage of models where a split happened) should approach 5% in both studies. Figure 5 shows the empirical type I error rates in Studies 1 and 2. In scenarios with homogeneous data and noise covariates, type I errors ranged from 0.2% to 22%, with an average of 4.4% across replications, which was very close to the expected value. In scenarios with heterogeneous data and noise covariates, however, type I error ranged from 7.8% to 58.4%, with an average of 27.2% split trees per forest.

[Insert Figure 5 here]

Variable importance estimates

As anticipated, variable importance estimates were negative or close to zero for all noise covariates in both Study 1 (ranging from -8.9 to -4.7) and Study 2 (ranging from -9.8 to -3.8). This finding shows the robustness of variable importance estimates to splits caused by type I errors, even in the presence of large type I error rates such as those observed in Study 2.

Figure 6 shows the average variable importance estimates in Study 3. To get a better understanding of the reliability (i.e., variability) of these estimates, we included 95% confidence intervals for each covariate. These intervals were computed based on the standard deviation of the variable importance values across all forests in the corresponding condition. The correct order of the informative predictors was recovered only in conditions with 1000 individuals (C2 and C4). In contrast, for conditions with 400 individuals (C1 and C3), predictor 3 was ranked slightly higher than predictor 2, though their confidence intervals overlapped almost entirely (see lower panels in Figure

6). Additionally, predictor 4 was indistinguishable from noise predictors in terms of importance in some replications. As expected, near-zero and negative estimates were obtained for noise covariates across all conditions. Note that, in conditions with 400 individuals, some categorical covariates lacked variable importance estimates. This occurred because the subgroups formed by the categories were smaller than the minimum sample size requested for splits in each node, making it impossible for the trees to use these covariates for splitting.

[Insert Figure 6 here]

Runtime

We recorded the computation time for the CT-SEM forests and variable importance analyses in minutes. The runtime of a CT-SEM forest can vary widely depending on multiple factors, such as the computing platform, the complexity of the model, the number of unique time intervals in the sample, or the number of repeated measures, among others. However, the runtimes presented here can serve as a rough guideline for researchers on what to expect under circumstances similar to the ones simulated here. The simulation was conducted on a [computer cluster of AMD EPYC 7713 64-Core processors using 64 cores per forest](#).

Table 2 shows the mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum runtime estimates of the CT-SEM forest and variable importance analyses across all replications in each condition in minutes. To obtain a rough estimate of the runtimes if only a single core was used, readers can multiply the values in Table 2 by 64. As expected, average runtimes are higher when there are informative predictors that can explain parameter heterogeneity, as well as with [increasing sample size and number of repeated measures](#).

Table 2.

Runtime estimates in minutes.

Study	Informative predictors	Analysis	Mean	SD	Min.	Max.
1	No	Forest	14.3	1.7	10.6	19.2
		Variable importance	0.6	0.06	0.4	0.9
		Total	14.9	1.7	11.1	19.9
2	Yes	Forest	17.5	4.7	12.6	71.6
		Variable importance	1.0	0.3	0.6	2.6
		Total	18.5	4.8	13.2	74.2
3.C1	Yes	Forest	13.8	1.7	11.1	23.8
		Variable importance	1.1	0.2	0.9	2.8
		Total	14.9	1.8	12.0	26.6
3.C2	Yes	Forest	42.2	7.4	30.3	125.6
		Variable importance	2.8	0.4	2.0	7.1
		Total	45.0	7.6	32.3	132.7
3.C3	Yes	Forest	62.5	6.3	53.2	85.0
		Variable importance	2.0	0.4	1.6	4.8
		Total	64.5	6.4	54.8	89.8
3.C4	Yes	Forest	222.9	11.1	198.3	258.3
		Variable importance	7.3	2.1	4.6	16.3
		Total	230.2	11.8	202.9	276.6

Note: SD = standard deviation, Min = minimum, Max = maximum.

Empirical example:

To illustrate the application and interpretation of CT-SEM forests, we present an empirical example using data from the Survey of Health, Ageing, and Retirement in Europe (SHARE; Börsch-Supan et al., 2013).

Data description

The SHARE is a multidisciplinary and cross-national panel study that collects life course data of European citizens on a wide range of variables spanning from physical and psychological health to socioeconomic status and family networks. By the year 2023, the SHARE includes data from more than 140.000 individuals aged 40 or older. For demonstration purposes, we selected a subsample of 2000 individuals that ranged in age from 41 to 85 years. The length of the measurement intervals varied both

across individuals and occasions, with a mean of 2.54 years and a standard deviation of 0.85 years

Our primary outcomes of interest were *depression* and *physical inactivity*. Depressive symptomatology was measured with the EURO-D scale (Prince et al., 1999). Originally developed to compare depressive symptoms across European countries, this scale consists of 12 dichotomous (yes/no) items, where higher values indicate a more severe symptomatology. Physical inactivity was measured with the two Likert-type items with four levels (1 = more than once a week, 2 = once a week, 3 = up to three times a month, 4 = hardly ever or never): 1) frequency of moderate physical activity (such as gardening, cleaning the car, or doing a walk), and 2) frequency of vigorous physical activity (sports, heavy housework, or a job involving physical labor), with higher values representing more inactivity or sedentarism. For each outcome measure, we computed an average score across all items, which was used for all subsequent analyses. In addition, we included a total of 15 different covariates to explore parameter heterogeneity in the dynamics between depression and physical inactivity. A summary of these covariates is included in Table 3. For ease of demonstration, we used only cases with complete data in the outcomes. Note that CT-SEM trees and forests allow missing values in the dependent variables, although they require complete data in the covariates.

Table 3.

Covariates used in the CT-SEM forest analysis

Covariate	Description	Variable type
gender	Biological sex	Dichotomous (Male/Female)
age	Age in years	Continuous
isced	International Standard Classification of Education (i.e., education level)	Ordinal (7 levels)

gali	Limitations in daily activities because of health	Dichotomous (Yes/No)
snsatis	Satisfaction with the social network	Continuous
propfriends	Proportion of friends in the social network	Continuous
fdistress	Financial distress (Is the household able to make ends meet?)	Ordinal (1=With great difficulty, 2=with some difficulty, 3=fairly easily, 4=easily)
bmi	Body mass index	Continuous
cjs	Current job situation	Multinomial (1 = retired, 2 = employed, 3 = unemployed, 4 = permanently sick, 5 = homemaker, 6 = other)
mstat	Marital status	Multinomial (1=Married, living with spouse, 2=registered partnership, 3=married, not living with spouse, 4=never married, 5=divorced, 6=widowed)
depmat	Material deprivation index (financial difficulties)	Continuous
depsoc	Social deprivation index (social isolation)	Continuous
drinking	Drinking problems. Have you drunk more than 2 glasses of alcohol almost every day in the last 3 months?	Dichotomous (Yes/No)
esmoked	Have you ever smoked daily for a period of at least one year?	Dichotomous (Yes/No)
nchild	Number of children	Count

Specification and estimation of the CT model

The first step of fitting a CT-SEM forest is the specification of a template model. For this, we employed the same model used in our simulation study (see Figure 1 and Equation 10). We specified this model using the *ctModel* function from the *ctsemOMX* package:

```
m <- ctModel(manifestNames = c("depression", "physical_activity"),
             latentNames = c("dep", "pa"),
             Tpoints = 7, LAMBDA = diag(2),
             DRIFT = "auto", DIFFUSION = "auto", MANIFESTVAR = "auto",
             TRAITVAR = "auto",
```

```

MANIFESTMEANS = matrix(0, nrow = 2, ncol = 1),
CINT = matrix(c("cint_dep", "cint_pa"), nrow = 2, ncol =
1))

```

In the code above, the `manifestNames` argument takes the names of the observed/manifest variables as they appear in the dataset, whereas the `latentNames` arguments is used to set the names of the latent processes. The argument `Tpoints` indicates the number of repeated measures. The remaining arguments are used to specify the parameters of the model, which is done by providing a string (e.g., "auto") or a matrix. Strings are used to freely estimate parameters, whereas numeric values (e.g., 1 or 0) are used to fix parameters to the corresponding value. For example, the `LAMBDA` argument was set to a diagonal matrix to link each observed variable to its underlying latent variable. The arguments `DRIFT`, `DIFFUSION`, `MANIFESTVAR`, and `TRAITVAR` were used to specify the drift, diffusion, [measurement error](#), and random intercept covariance matrices, respectively. Here, we used the "auto" string to indicate that all the parameters in these matrices were freely estimated ([except for the measurement error covariance](#)). Finally, we requested the estimation of two CT intercepts (one for each latent process) by setting the parameters within the `CINT` argument to "cint_dep" and "cint_pa".

Next, the parameters of the specified model were estimated using the `ctFit` function:

```

fit <- ctFit(dat = dfwide, ctmodelobj = m, retryattempts = 25,
stationary = "all")

```

Here, we provided the `dat` argument with `dfwide`, which is the name of the database in wide format ([for instructions on preparing the data or converting it to long format, see Driver et al., 2017](#)). The CT model `m` specified in the previous step was supplied to

ctFit using the `ctmodelobj` argument. The argument `retryattempts` determines the number of estimation attempts in case of an initial non-convergence, which was set to 25. For the sake of simplicity, we set the argument `stationary` to "all", which computes the means and variances of the first measurement occasion as functions of the other parameters of the model, reducing the number of parameters that are freely estimated.

Table 4 shows the parameter estimates obtained after fitting the model to the entire sample. Focusing on the parameters for a fixed interval of 1 year, it is possible to see a strong carry-over effect in *depression* and *physical inactivity* separately, but the cross-lagged effects are virtually zero. A large portion of the variance of the process was trait-like stable differences and measurement error, which suggests that the predictive power of the model fitted to the entire sample was low and there was little intra-individual variability. To explore the presence of parameter heterogeneity in this sample and identify relevant predictors of such heterogeneity, we proceed to fit a CT-SEM forest.

Table 4.

Parameter estimates of the continuous time model fitted to the entire sample.

	CT value	Std. Error	DT value*
drift_y1	-0.16	0.04	0.85
drift_y2_y1	0.00	0.02	0.00
drift_y1_y2	0.01	0.01	-0.01
drift_y2	-0.11	0.02	0.91
diff_y1	0.11	0.02	0.09
diff_y2_y1	0.04	0.01	0.03
diff_y2	0.10	0.01	0.09
cinty1	0.00	0.00	0.00
cinty2	0.00	0.00	0.00
traitvar_y1	0.37	0.03	0.37

traitvar_y2_y1	0.18	0.02	0.18
traitvar_y2	0.23	0.06	0.23
error_y1	0.34	0.02	0.35
error_y2	0.47	0.02	0.49

Note: DT values are computed for an interval of $\Delta t = 1$ year.

Fitting the CT-SEM forest

Building a CT-SEM forest requires setting the hyper-parameters that guide the tree and forest creation process via the `semtree.control` and the `semforest.control` functions:

```
ctrl <- semtree.control(method = "score", min.bucket = 150, bonferroni
= T)

frst_ctrl <- semforest.control(num.trees = 1000, control = ctrl, mtry
= 4)
```

In `semtree.control`, the `method` argument allows the user to choose between different covariate testing procedures (for more details, see Arnold et al., 2021 and Brandmaier et al., 2013). We set it to "score" to make use of a score-guided approach. The argument `min.bucket` determines the minimum sample size of a node. We set it to 150 to prevent the creation of subgroups smaller than 150 individuals because the parameter estimates can become unreliable with small sample sizes. Finally, setting `bonferroni` to `TRUE` applies a Bonferroni adjustment to the p -values at each split to control for multiple testing. On the other hand, the `semforest.control` function takes the tree control object `ctrl` as an input, and uses its arguments to guide the creation of trees. Here, the number of trees in the forest was set to 1000 via the `num.trees` argument, and the number of covariates entering each tree was set to $m = \log_2(15) \approx 4$ (where 15 is the total number of covariates in the dataset) using the `mtry` argument.

The next step is to fit the CT-SEM forest using the `semforest` function:

```
forest <- semforest(model = fit, data = dfwide, control = forest_ctrl,  
predictors = prednames)
```

Here, we provided the `semforest` with the template model (using the `model` argument), the database in wide format (using the `data` argument), the hyper-parameters of the tree and forest (using the `control` argument), and the names of the covariates in the data frame `dfwide` (using the `predictors` argument). After running the CT-SEM forest, the last step is to provide the forest object to the `varimp` function to compute variable importance estimates:

```
vim <- varimp(forest)
```

As in the simulation study, the analysis of the empirical data was performed on an [AMD EPYC 7713](#) processor using 64 cores. The runtimes were 58 hours for the CT-SEM forest and 22 minutes for the variable importance estimates. These estimates can be either printed to the R console or visualized with the `plot` function, as depicted in Figure 7. We found that *gali* (i.e., limitations of daily activities because of health) was the most important variable, with an average absolute increase of $-2LL$ of 393, which corresponds to an average decrease in loglikelihood of about 1.52%. As explained above, this is the drop in loglikelihood averaged over all the trees in the forest when the variable *gali* is randomly permuted. The second most influential variable was *social deprivation*, with an average decrease in loglikelihood of 1.46%, followed by *material deprivation*, *financial distress*, *gender*, and *isced* (i.e., education level), with average decreases ranging from 1.38% to 0.8%. On the other hand, variables such as *number of children* explained virtually zero heterogeneity.

[Insert Figure 7 here]

The information provided by CT-SEM forests can be used in multiple ways, and in the Discussion section we present an overview of some applications. For illustrative purposes, we fitted a CT-SEM tree to the SHARE data including the ten most important predictors, and fixed the depth of the tree to a maximum of three levels per branch using the `max.depth` argument of the `semtree.control` function. The resulting tree can be visualized with the `plot` function, as depicted in Figure 8. This tree performed splits based on the covariates *depmat* (material deprivation), *depsoc* (social deprivation index), and *gali* (limitations in daily activities because of health), and identified five subgroups with different parameter values. From top to bottom, the first split was performed between those with scores lower and larger than 0.20 in the material deprivation index. This index is an aggregate measure that ranges from 0 to 1 and is comprised of 12 items that assess financial difficulties and failure in affordability of diverse basic needs (e.g., groceries, clothing, dentist, etc.). The resulting subgroups were both further partitioned based on their scores in the social deprivation index. This index is also an aggregate measure that ranges from 0 to 1 and assesses diverse aspects such as social isolation, access to health and social services, or literacy, among others. For individuals with material and social deprivation indices lower than ~0.21 the covariate *gali* was selected, leading to two subgroups characterized by the presence and absence, respectively, of limitations in daily activities due to health issues. Figure 8 also shows the CT parameter estimates characterizing the subgroups in each of the leaf nodes.

[Figure 8]

Figure 9 shows the strength of the autoregressive and standardized cross-lagged parameters as functions of the time intervals for the subgroups in each leaf node. Standardization of the cross-lagged parameters makes them comparable across nodes

and is obtained through multiplication by the ratios of the corresponding elements in the asymptotic diffusion matrix. The strength of the autoregressive effects of *depression* and *physical inactivity* was similar in Nodes 4 and 8. In Nodes 6 and 9, characterized by individuals with scores larger than $\sim .22$ in the social deprivation index, the autoregressive effect of physical inactivity was stronger, meaning that scores in physical inactivity seemed to be more stable over time (more dependent on previous scores) compared to depression scores. The opposite pattern was observed in Node 5, characterized by individuals with low scores in both the social and material deprivation indices and with no limitations in daily activities due to health issues. The cross-lagged effects were also heterogeneous across nodes. In individuals associated with Node 4 (low material and social deprivation but with limitations in daily activities) and Node 6 (scores $< .20$ in material deprivation but $\geq .22$ in social deprivation), the processes of depression and physical inactivity were positively but only slightly interrelated over time. On the other hand, individuals in Node 5 (low material and social deprivation and no limitations in daily activities) showed negative interrelations, meaning that higher scores in depression temporally preceded higher levels of physical activity, and vice versa. In Node 8 (scores $\geq .20$ in material deprivation but $< .21$ in social deprivation) the cross-lagged effect from physical inactivity to depression was virtually zero across lags, whereas the effect of depression on physical inactivity was only slightly negative. Finally, for individuals in Node 9 (with high scores in both social and material deprivation) higher scores in physical inactivity (i.e., more sedentarism) were predictive of higher levels of depression over time, whereas higher scores in depression were predictive of lower scores in physical inactivity (i.e., more exercise). Some differences were also found in the CT intercepts: as expected, individuals with no limitations in their daily activities were less depressed and more physically active (Node 5), on

average, than those with limitations due to health (Node 4). Similarly, individuals with high material and social deprivation scores (Node 9), were on average more depressed and less physically active compared to the rest of the groups. Although we use empirical data, we would like to remind the reader that we are only considering a subsample, that a tree as compared to a forest can be notoriously unstable (see also the Discussion section), and that the example was chosen for illustrative purposes. Any substantial interpretation would require a more thorough investigation.

[Figure 9]

Discussion

In the present paper, we presented score-guided CT-SEM forests, an integration of CT models and score-guided SEM forests. CT-SEM forests are a powerful approach to explore predictors of heterogeneity in change and dynamics, while accounting for heterogeneity in the intervals between measurement occasions. CT-SEM forests mitigate the instability of single CT-SEM trees and provide robust and reliable estimates of the predictive performance of a set of covariates. This approach builds upon the work of Brandmaier et al. (2018), who introduced CT-SEM trees based on likelihood ratios, and Arnold et al. (2024), who implemented score-based tests for the recursive partitioning of CT models. In the present manuscript, we took these foundational works a step further by introducing the first implementation, systematic evaluation, and empirical application of score-based CT-SEM forests.

Summary of findings

The results of the simulation study showed that, **in scenarios with 1000 individuals**, the proposed CT-SEM forest was capable of prioritizing and correctly sorting sets of informative covariates, as well as discerning them from uninformative

noise. This occurred consistently across all replications in those conditions. However, in scenarios with 400 individuals, the 2nd and 3rd most important covariates were often incorrectly ranked, with one frequently recovered in place of the other. Furthermore, the 4th predictor was indistinguishable from a noise covariate in many replications. Increasing the number of repeated measures led to more reliable estimates of variable importance, although this improvement was much less pronounced than the effect of increasing the sample size.

Notably, we observed that the trees within the forests exhibited a tendency to split when there was heterogeneity in the data but none of the covariates were predictors of such heterogeneity, resulting in high type-I error rates. This may occur because the score-based algorithm for covariate and split selection is overly sensitive to unobserved heterogeneity, leading to an overestimation of the covariates' ability to account for it. A recent study by Debelak and Driver (in press) on score-based tests in Item Response Theory similarly reported elevated type-I error rates when ability groups were inaccurately defined, supporting the hypothesis that score-based tests may be sensitive to unobserved heterogeneity. However, a more detailed exploration is needed to clarify the precise causes of these elevated type-I error rates and their implications for group comparisons and covariate selection. The increased type-I error rate indicates that the presence of a covariate in a single tree structure does not guarantee its importance as a predictor of parameter heterogeneity, further highlighting the importance of forests. Variable importance analyses showed near-zero estimates for the covariates guiding these splits, correctly identifying them as irrelevant predictors. This suggests that inflated type-I error rates may not be critical for a CT-SEM forest analysis.

An important aspect of CT-SEM forests is the runtime. In both the simulation study and the empirical example we ran the analyses in parallel using 64 cores. In the

simulation study, we obtained average runtimes ranging from 15 to 230 minutes, depending on the combination of N and T , whereas the analysis of the empirical example took approximately 3480 minutes. This discrepancy is mainly due to the number individuals in the empirical database, which was 2000 instead of 1000, and the number of unique sets of time intervals. In the simulation study, measurement interval length varied randomly from 0.6 to 1.4, resulting in 9 possible interval lengths. In the empirical database, however, time interval length varied from 1 to 5.3, and the number of possible intervals was 40, thus increasing the number of computations.

Practical recommendations

Continuous-time SEM forests are useful to identify predictors of parameter heterogeneity in dynamic models. However, it is not always clear how this information can be interpreted in a substantive way or used to construct explanatory models. In fact, there are very few suggestions in the literature on how to proceed once the relevant predictors have been identified. In this section, we explore some alternatives.

In their seminal work, Brandmaier et al. (2016) proposed incorporating relevant covariates as exogenous predictors in the original template model. In this approach, one or more relevant predictors are selected, and then passed through a SEM tree analysis to identify the best partitions. The covariates are then dichotomized based on the tree-determined cutpoints, and either integrated as exogenous predictors into the model or used to build a multigroup model. The limitation of this approach is that it is not always clear which predictors are sufficiently important to be considered for further analyses. Some authors (e.g., Breiman & Cutler, 2008) have suggested using a z -score test to determine whether the importance of a predictor is significantly different from zero. However, the power of this test depends largely on the number of trees, which is an arbitrary choice of the researcher, and thus any statements of significance are unadvised.

As suggested by Strobl et al. (2009), a better option is to consider all predictors with a positive variable importance for further exploration. The CT-SEM forest used in our empirical dataset yielded 15 predictors with importance higher than zero. Including all these predictors as exogenous covariates would lead to an overly complex and barely interpretable model. Instead, building modified models with only one predictor each, as demonstrated by Van Lissa et al. (2023), can be a more practical approach. Note, however, that this approach does not address nonlinear effects or interactions and only renders descriptive results that should be not used for inference.

As shown previously, variable importance information can be used to build a CT-SEM tree including only a subset of the most relevant predictors. Pruning or limiting the number of nodes of this tree will likely produce an illustrative and easily interpretable structure where some relevant subgroups and their specific parameter differences can be identified. However, such a tree would not account for all the covariates and their interactions, and it would suffer from the instability problems of decision tree algorithms, meaning that the resulting structure may not be reliable. If this approach is used, we recommend fitting the CT-SEM tree to a few subsets of individuals from the sample to check if they consistently yield the same structure. For another empirical application of this approach in the context of CT-SEM trees, we refer the readers to Arnold et al. (2024).

As an alternative to variable importance, researchers can explore the internal structure of the data using proximity measures. Inspired by the ideas of Breiman and Cutler (2014), clustering based on proximity can be used to uncover heterogeneity in the dataset. The concept is rooted in the intuition that similar cases should end up in the same leaf nodes of trees within a forest, indicating shared values of variables along the path to the root node. Using multidimensional scaling, it is possible to project these

proximities onto lower-dimensional coordinates represented by the covariates. This, in turn, can be used to obtain graphical representations of how individuals with similar parameter estimates are clustered in relation to their position in such covariates. For an empirical application of proximity measures, we refer the readers to Brandmaier et al. (2016).

Finally, CT-SEM forests can be used to predict parameters for individuals with specific combinations of scores in the predictors. This approach involves averaging the parameter estimates across all trees, leading to a vector of parameter values for each combination of predictor scores. Thus, feeding the CT-SEM forests with new cases would yield a vector of predicted parameter estimates for each individual based on their combinations of values in the predictors. It is important to note, however, that these predicted parameters *were estimated from group data and* do not characterize specific cases. Instead, they *reflect average dynamics of* the group or population from which the individual was extracted. Hence, this strategy can be useful to characterize specific groups or populations, but it *may not be suitable for capturing* change and dynamics at the individual level. For an empirical application of this approach in the context of longitudinal SEM forests, we refer the readers to Van Lissa et al. (2023).

Benefits, limitations, and future directions

Continuous-time SEM forests bring significant improvements over previous discrete-time implementations (see Brandmaier et al., 2016, Arnold et al. 2021). While the advantages of CT models *over DT models* have been outlined in the introduction (see also de Haan-Rietdijk et al., 2017), understanding their impact on tree and forest construction is by no means obvious. We believe that CT-SEM forests address at least three major drawbacks of their DT counterpart. Firstly, in DT models, heterogeneity in the spacing between intervals can introduce bias in the parameter estimates, potentially

leading to inaccurate partitions and biased variable importance estimates. Secondly, any conclusions drawn from a DT analysis regarding partitions and variable importance are restricted to the specific time interval used. This obscures the true influence of predictors on the underlying dynamics, impeding generalization to other time intervals. Thirdly, heterogeneity in the time intervals and parameter heterogeneity may interact in a highly complicated fashion, leading to untrustworthy results if not properly accounted for. The integration of SEM trees and forests with CT models offers a solution to these problems.

The general limitations of SEM forests in the context of cross-sectional and DT modeling have been thoroughly discussed elsewhere (see Brandmaier et al., 2013, 2016). For this reason, we will primarily focus on the limitations arising from their combination with CT models and from our current software implementation. As outlined earlier, CT models are more susceptible to estimation problems such as local solutions compared to other models. If the model has a reasonable fit to the data and the sample size is sufficient, this should not be problematic in most cases. However, as the sample is repeatedly split along the branches of the trees, some of the nodes may be affected by estimation issues, which may lead to unreliable results. In a similar vein, the computational burden imposed by SEM forests is greatly increased when combined with CT models. [In our empirical example, conducting CT-SEM forest and variable importance analyses based on a model featuring 12 parameters and a sample size of 2000 individuals took approximately 58 hours.](#) These runtimes can be further increased in datasets with larger sample sizes or more unique time intervals, as well as in forests with more trees. While this may not be particularly problematic if a cluster computer is available, it limits the application of CT-SEM forests on standard desktop computers. Future endeavors should focus on optimizing algorithms for CT modeling and recursive

partitioning to make CT-SEM forests less time-consuming and more accessible for empirical researchers.

An additional limitation of forests in general is their interpretation. Variable importance estimates provide useful information about the overall relevance of a set of covariates and are a good starting point for generating new hypotheses. However, the information they provide is highly aggregated, making it difficult to understand the relationships between the variables. Moreover, SEM forests do not identify the specific parameters responsible for the explained heterogeneity, nor do they clarify whether such predictions involve interactions or main effects. In the machine learning literature, some interpretation techniques, such as *partial dependence*, *accumulated local effects*, or *representative trees*, have been proposed to better understand the relationship between the predictors and the outcome in trees and forests (see Banerjee et al., 2012; Henninger et al., 2023; Laabs et al., 2023). An interesting future direction could be the adaptation of these techniques to the context of model-based forests, as well as the development of new techniques. For example, the difference between each pair of parameters resulting from a split could be averaged across all trees in the SEM forest to yield indicators of how much each parameter changes in relation to each covariate. This and other potential indicators could contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the intricate relationships captured by SEM forests, improving their interpretability and applicability in empirical research.

As opposed to CT-SEM forests, CT-SEM trees may initially seem more clear and interpretable. However, when parameter values are compared across nodes, it is not always easy to visually discern relevant differences across groups. This challenge becomes particularly pronounced in models with a large number of parameters, where the interpretation of between-group differences can be obscured by the complexity of

the model. In a recent study, Orzek & Voelkle (2023) employed LASSO regularization to improve parameter interpretation in CT models. This technique could be applied in combination with CT-SEM trees to shrink irrelevant parameter differences towards zero, while retaining true-nonzero differences. This could simplify the interpretation of parameters in the leaf nodes and facilitate group comparisons, although at the expense of increased computational runtime.

The sample size and number of repeated measures required to fit a CT-SEM forest depends on factors such as data quality, model complexity, the degree of model-data fit, and the level of observed heterogeneity, among others. In our study, we found that sample sizes of 400 individuals were sufficient to distinguish relevant covariates from irrelevant ones, but not to reliably recover the exact order of importance for some covariates. Conversely, sample sizes of 1000 individuals appeared to achieve this goal. Likewise, alternative combinations of hyperparameters beyond those used here might improve CT-SEM forest performance.

Finally, the recursive partitioning of CT models could be improved by interfacing the *semtree* package with other packages for CT analysis, such as *ctsem* (Driver & Voelkle, 2018) or *dynr* (Ou et al., 2019). Our current implementation is built on the *ctsemOMX* package, because both *ctsemOMX* and *semtree* use the *OpenMx* package (Hunter, 2018; Neale et al., 2016) for model estimation. It is important to note that the high computational demands observed in our study could possibly be due to the choice of this specific software. Likewise, the *ctsem* package surpasses *ctsemOMX* in terms of functionality, including Bayesian estimation methods, hierarchical modeling, and various optimizers from the *rstan* package (Stan Development Team, 2023) that may improve runtime and allow for further extensions of CT-SEM trees and forests. Likewise, integrating CT model-based recursive partitioning with *dynr* would possibly

allow to estimate trees and forests using CT models that are not currently available in the *ctsem* environment.

Conclusion

In this manuscript, we presented the first implementation and detailed investigation of CT-SEM forests: a model-based recursive partitioning approach that allows to explore predictors of heterogeneity in continuous-time change and dynamics. As demonstrated in our Monte Carlo study, the proposed method is capable of correctly identifying relevant predictors and discerning them from noise, as well as accurately recovering the true order of importance of such predictors. The simulation study, along with our empirical application of the method, serves as a proof of principle for the feasibility and applicability of CT-SEM forests in empirical research. Although the method has some limitations and room for improvement, we believe CT-SEM forests hold great potential for the investigation of parameter heterogeneity in longitudinal research. We hope that the empirical example presented here, along with the code available in the supplementary website, will help researchers on future applications of CT-SEM forests.

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Appendix A

In this section, we explain how the test statistics for covariate evaluation are computed based on the cumulative score process (CSP) matrix. In conditions of parameter homogeneity, each column of the CSP matrix converges in distribution to a univariate Brownian bridge (see Hjort & Koning, 2002): a stochastic process that starts and ends at zero and has the most variability in the middle. In conditions of parameter heterogeneity, on the other hand, the distribution of the columns of the CSP matrix should deviate from the Brownian bridge distribution. The extent of this deviation can be computed by aggregating the cumulative score process into a single scalar, which serves as a test statistic. To test the hypothesis of parameter homogeneity, critical values and p -values can be obtained by applying the same aggregation to the Brownian bridge. As outlined in the *structural equation model trees* section, there are different ways of aggregating the CSP matrix that lead to test statistics with different properties. In our implementation of CT-SEM trees, we used the following test statistics.

For continuous covariates, we used the maximum Lagrange multiplier ($\max LM$) test (Merkle & Zeileis, 2013):

$$\max LM = \max_{i=\underline{i}, \dots, \bar{i}} \left\{ \left[\frac{i}{N} \left(1 - \frac{i}{N} \right) \right]^{-1} \sum_{k=1}^q CSP_{i,k}^2 \right\} \quad (A1)$$

that sums all the $k = 1, \dots, q$ cumulative scores for each individual $i = 1, \dots, N$, leading to a $N \times 1$ vector, and then takes the maximum of this vector. Note that Equation A1

contains a scaling term $\left[\frac{i}{N} \left(1 - \frac{i}{N} \right) \right]^{-1}$ that increases the sensitivity for peaks before and after the middle of the process. The limitation of this statistic is that individuals with very small or very large values in the covariate under scrutiny may cause instability in the test statistic, so they need to be omitted. Therefore, one needs to specify a lower (\underline{i})

and upper (\bar{i}) threshold to define the range of data considered for analysis.

Consequently, any parameter shifts outside the interval $[\underline{l}, \dots, \bar{l}]$ are not considered.

For ordinal covariates, we used the ordinal Lagrange multiplier test statistic $\max LM_0$ proposed by Merkle et al. (2014):

$$\max LM_0 = \max_{l=1, \dots, m-1} \left\{ \left[\frac{n_l}{N} \left(1 - \frac{n_l}{N} \right) \right]^{-1} \sum_{k=1}^q CBSP_{l,k}^2 \right\} \quad (A2)$$

where $l = 1, 2, \dots, m - 1$ are the levels of the covariate. In this test statistic, individuals are first grouped into $m - 1$ bins corresponding to the first $m - 1$ levels of the covariate. Then, we sum the individual scores in each bin and cumulate the sums, obtaining a $(m - 1) \times q$ matrix. In Equation A2, this matrix is referred to as $CBSP_{l,k}$. Similar to the $\max LM$ statistic for continuous covariates, the $\max LM_0$ statistic also has a scaling term $\frac{n_l}{N} \left(1 - \frac{n_l}{N} \right)$, where n_l is the number of individuals in the l -th bin.

For categorical variables in nominal scale, we used the Lagrange multiplier (LM) test statistic proposed by Hjort & Koning (2002):

$$LM = \sum_{l=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^q (BSP_{l,k} - BSP_{l-1,k})^2 \quad (A3)$$

In the LM test statistic we first group the individual scores into m bins corresponding to the m levels of the covariate. Then, we sum the scores in each bin, yielding a $BSP_{l,k}$ matrix of dimensions $m \times q$. This matrix contains the scores of all $k = 1, 2, \dots, q$ parameters from individuals associated with each l -th level of the covariate. Next, we compute the squared differences of summed scores across bins, resulting again in a $m \times q$ matrix. Note that, for the first level of the covariate, the difference becomes $BSP_{1,k} - BSP_{0,k}$. Here, $BSP_{0,k}$ is not associated with any of the levels of the covariate

and thus it is set to zero. Finally, the LM statistic is obtained by “summing the sums” across all bins (m) and parameters (q).

Appendix B

Table B1.

Description of covariates in Study 1 and 2 of the simulation study.

Covariate	Scale of measurement	Number of levels
Covariate 1	Continuous	-
Covariate 2	Continuous	-
Covariate 3	Continuous	-
Covariate 4	Continuous	-
Covariate 5	Ordinal	4
Covariate 6	Ordinal	4
Covariate 7	Ordinal	3
Covariate 8	Ordinal	5
Covariate 9	Multinomial	3
Covariate 10	Multinomial	4
Covariate 11	Multinomial	5
Covariate 12	Multinomial	6
Covariate 13	Dichotomous	2
Covariate 14	Dichotomous	2
Covariate 15	Dichotomous	2

Table B2.

Description of covariates in Study 3 of the simulation study.

Covariate	Scale of measurement	Number of levels
Predictor 1	Continuous	-
Predictor 2	Dichotomous	2
Predictor 3	Ordinal	5
Predictor 4	Multinomial	4
Covariate 1	Continuous	-
Covariate 2	Continuous	-
Covariate 3	Continuous	-
Covariate 4	Ordinal	5
Covariate 5	Ordinal	4
Covariate 6	Ordinal	3
Covariate 7	Multinomial	3
Covariate 8	Multinomial	4
Covariate 9	Multinomial	5
Covariate 10	Dichotomous	2

Figures

Figure 1

Continuous-time specification of a random-intercept cross-lagged panel model.

Note. The shaded equations illustrate the transformations required to constrain the DT parameters to CT parameters for any given time interval.

Figure 2.

Example of a SEM tree.

Figure 3.

Example of the results of a variable importance analysis.

Figure 4.

Tree structure used for Study 2 and Study 3.

Figure 5.

Empirical type I error rates of Study 1 and Study 2.

Study 1.

Study 2.

Figure 6.

Variable importance estimates with 95% confidence intervals of Study 3.

Figure 7.

Variable importance as predictors of heterogeneity in depressive symptoms and physical inactivity over time.

Figure 8.

Continuous-time SEM tree modeling the interplay between depressive symptoms and physical inactivity over time.

Figure 9.

Autoregressive and standardized cross-lagged parameters as functions of measurement intervals.

